

THREE DIMENSIONAL AUTOMATED LONG-TERM MONITORING OF BIO-BASED BUILDING ELEMENTS IN OUTDOOR CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an innovative method for automated long-term, outdoor monitoring and analysis of materials, surpassing current techniques. It introduces a highly autonomous and resilient monitoring protocol utilizing low-cost depth cameras, enabling frequent observation over months. The paper evaluates existing 3D capture technology for outdoor suitability and proposes a method, that enables comprehensive examination of changes in both material appearance and geometry over extended periods. It develops qualitative and quantitative analysis of captured data merging depth data with 2D imagery. To track and quantify deformations at both global and feature levels a further voxel-based method is developed. The method is evaluated in two case studies, where the deformation of 3D printed bio-polymer panels is monitored, revealing their interaction with weather conditions. This research seamlessly integrates with material and design development, advocating for a new building practice grounded in real-world structural behaviors.

Keywords: long-term monitoring, material behavior, bio-polymer, 3D printing, weathering.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Architecture, Engineering, and Construction industry (AEC) benefits from monitoring systems using human inspection and increasingly computer vision to detect failure and deformations in buildings and structures [1][2]. However, there are inherent limitations to existing approaches: human inspection is labor-intensive and therefore expensive, which results in the maximization of intervals between inspections. It is as well prone to error [3]. Computer vision can be automated [4], but is limited in detecting features in changing outdoor conditions with varying illumination [5]. New approaches towards monitoring are required, that work independently of humans, the limitations of the flat picture plane captures of common cameras and can capture in short intervals. Such approaches are essential when the three-dimensional behavior of materials over time needs to be analyzed. These appear for instance in the novel class of bio-materials in construction, such as bio-polymers, which could be one of the pillars in the transition of the building industry into a material practice based on renewable and circular resources [6]. Bio-polymers, like many other bio-based material classes, are characterized by large state changes in response to factors such as humidity and temperature and short life-spans depending on their environmental setting. Observation and analysis of the behavior of these materials in real-world conditions are essential for future use in the building industry (Figure 7). Studying the behavior of bio-based materials requires us to establish knowledge and tools that can detect change and reaction to environments, as in warpage and shrinkage, using automated 3D scans. While the subject of this research is bound to bio-based materials, the developed method is not limited to it and can be implemented in other scenarios.

1.1 Methods for Outdoor 3D scanning - State of the art

Current approaches for long-term observation of structures and materials are either concerned with the weathering of materials or the detection of deterioration of buildings and infrastructures. While human inspection is the predominant method of monitoring, the use of computer vision has shown significant improvement in the detection of weathering on materials [4]. Long-time observations use time-lapses in some cases. These are however inefficient for tracking three-dimensional movements of structures [4], as for example, warpage and shrinkage look the same in the flat picture plane. 3D capture via photogrammetry or 3D scanning [7] solves this problem and is used for the detection of deformation of structures over time via an overlay of designed and as-built [8][9]. More automated analysis of 3D scans is used for crack detection in concrete structures [10][11] or in steel structures to detect corrosion [12]. Current methods establish differences between the initial and final state but do not allow for reasoning about cause and effect, as for example a consecutive registration of a structure over time would. Long-term observations are currently limited to time-lapse cameras which have limitations for example, in detecting shrinkage and warpage as they look the same in 2D captures [4]. A gap is identified in respect to the tracking of three-dimensional changes. For this a monitoring system based on 3D capturing devices needs to be implemented which can record at least daily. A use in outdoor environments requires consideration of both changing weather conditions and potentially malicious human intervention. This 3D scanner should be encapsulated and have an open interface, so that it can be programmed and adapted to site conditions and generate data ready to be analyzed according to project needs. It should as well fit into a academic budget.

2 AN AUTOMATED 3D MONITORING SYSTEM

Based on the gap analysis we develop a framework for acquiring 3D data of objects in outdoor environments at short intervals, surpassing the constraints of conventional methods. This method allows for storing 3D time-based data and visualizing the changes over time to establish data points and vectors to quantify changes in different elements over time (Figure 7). Our approach is conducted with low-cost components: a depth camera, IoT (Internet of Things) sensors, and a single-board computer to schedule 3D scans and buffer data. This system is embedded into a monitoring framework [4], that has been developed within the EU funded EMA (Eco-Metabolistic Architecture) project. This framework provides infrastructure and tools for automation, remote control, secure storage in the cloud and automated data analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Setup of the monitoring system with deployed sensors and data flow.

2.1 Outdoor 3D scanning

The four principal categories of available 3D scanning technologies are laser scanners, light scanners, Coordinate measuring machines (CMM) (Contact-based 3D scanning), and photogrammetry, [13], which can be used in outdoor conditions. However, as their features, such as range accuracy, resolution, speed, portability, field of view, color capturing capability, cost, and adaptability to the outdoor environment [7][14][15] differ, the first step in our research was to explore the best fit to 24/7 autonomous outdoor 3D scanning.

2.1.1 Choice of 3D scanning technologies

The first criterion - *autonomous action* - excluded 3D scanning approaches, which require human interaction, such as CMM. The second criterion - *the ability to operate in all weather conditions* - narrows the field further, as many 3D scanners, like the ones used for building surveys, are not waterproofed and as well so expensive that they cannot be left unattended. Cheaper 3D scanners that are designed for outdoor use, have been developed for applications in automotive and autonomous robots. These e.g., Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) based systems trade however precision with speed and are tuned to detect distant objects, which contradicts our needs for monitoring of building elements. Optical 3D scanning systems have been popularised not least with the introduction of the Microsoft Kinect, which has been widely adopted in academic research and industrial development, not at least, as it is very affordable with a price below 400€. Mapping depth through either structured light or time of flight calculations. This device, with no moving parts, is inexpensive, and designed to detect close objects e.g., in small rooms.

2.1.2 Indoor validation of chosen 3D scanner technology

We initiated a detailed investigation to evaluate the suitability of commercial depth cameras, particularly in terms of range accuracy and ability to adapt to outdoor conditions. We investigate two commercial portable depth-sensing cameras, with available SDK (Software Development Kits) to operate them in autonomous mode: Intel Realsense LIDAR camera L515 and Azure Kinect 3D scanner. We built a test rig of 200cmx140cm, which holds a 20cmx30cm biopolymer 3D printed sample with the camera positioned perpendicular to it. The first test considers the relation accuracy to the range. This reveals that the Intel Realsense L515 camera has the best result at only 40cm distance, covering a field of view of only 40cmx40cm (Figure 2). Therefore, it is not suitable to monitor most architectural scale elements. The Azure Kinect provides two settings for the field of view: at 100cm distance from the test rig it covers in Wide Field of View (WFOV) mode a range of 200cmx200cm, and in the Narrow Field of View (NFOV) mode, it covers a hexagon with 85cm for sides. However, because the camera emits here the same amount of IR rays, but on a smaller field, the NFOV mode has a higher resolution. A test of the accuracy of the scans and their general noise level was conducted by comparing the results of two 3D scans taken from same position under controlled indoor light conditions (Figure 2) and showed that the deviation between scans is in a range of 0.15mm - 3.10mm, which is again in the range of terrestrial 3d scanners.

2.1.3 Long-time outdoor 3D scanning

Outdoor conditions challenge vision-based systems in multiple ways such as shadows, glow, bad weather, and among others [16]. For the development of 3D scanning outdoors, precipitation and the interference of IR rays from the sun with IR rays from the 3D scanner [17] were expected to be the major challenges. To test the fit of the Azure Kinect technology to outdoor 3D conditions, we took scans during summer in direct sunlight in WFOV and NFOV modes. The assessment of the scan quality (Figure 3) highlights the sensitivity of the IR-based scanning technologies to sunlight: areas exposed to direct sunlight in the scan exhibit missing points in the point cloud, appear hollow and demonstrate a significant increase in the overall

Figure 2: (Left) Indoor test: Setup of the test rig with Intel Realsense L515 Lidar at the tools optimal range (40cm), (Right) Test of the accuracy of Azure Kinect 3D in repeated scans by comparing deviation of two consecutive scan.

noise level. We conclude that the Azure Kinect can scan in sufficient resolution for our task, yet only if scans are taken at a time with low IR levels.

Figure 3: Outdoor test under direct sunlight: (left) wide field of view, (right) narrow field of view 3D scan.

2.1.4 Adaptation of 3D scanning technique to outdoor conditions

The Azure Kinect camera is not designed for outdoor environments and is specified to work in the temperature range of 10-25°C and a humidity range of 8-90% Relative Humidity [18], therefore, a 3D printed enclosure covered with water protection resin was designed and employed on the camera (Figure 4). An initial outdoor test revealed that due to the camera's upward-facing orientation rainwater accumulated in the lens's outer layer. Initially, a glass cover was trialed to prevent this, but it compromised the 3D scans' quality. Consequently, the camera's orientation was adjusted to face downward, complemented by an aluminum cover to shield it from direct rain. Extensive weather protection measures have been applied to the minicomputer, cables, and power supply as well. To mitigate the impact of Infrared Ray (IR) on scans we employ

(a) Monitoring rig with 8 small bio-polymer samples, enclosures for electronics and Kinect in the first experiment. (b) Improved position of Kinect and aluminum rain cover.

Figure 4: Long-term material monitoring rig installed in Copenhagen at the Royal Danish Academy.

data from from a local weather station and luminosity sensors. We use the EMA sensor framework [4] to automatically determine appropriate conditions and trigger the daily 3D scans with minimal IR interference and upload these to the cloud.

2.1.5 Outdoor validation of the accuracy of 3D scans with Azure Kinect

In order to validate the accuracy of the 3D scanning process in outdoor conditions, we select two points on each panel: The first point is on the top right corner of the panel, which is connected to the timber support and the second point is on the bottom right unsupported corner of the panel. Measuring these points on the rig and in the 3D data allows us to establish data on the accuracy of the measurements and the margin of error. The comparison between the distance of these points to the back plate in the 3D scan and on the rig (Table. 1)(Figure 5) shows that the accuracy of the measurements was 4.16 mm on average, which is a value similar to the tolerances of e.g. 3D laser scanners used for building survey [14]. The results from the table also reveal that on the wide field of view mode, the measurements in the outer regions of the view have lower accuracy and the closer we get to the center the higher the depth camera accuracy becomes. Moreover, the maximum deviation as shown in the table 1 in both 3D scan and manual measurements is equal to 50mm and 49mm, respectively.

Table 1: Assessment of the accuracy of Azure Kinect measurements in outdoor conditions via sample points.

Measured Distance (mm)	Panel	1	2	3	5	6	7	Average
Outdoor rig Top Right Corner		47	40	30	40	25	40	37.00
Outdoor rig Bottom Right Corner		35	50	45	40	15	45	38.33
3D scan		41	49	42	40	30	35	39.50
Difference Top and Bottom corner		12	10	15	0	10	5	8.66
Difference Highest Corner and 3D scan		6	1	3	0	5	10	4.16

Figure 5: Point cloud of the rig with points colored according to the distance to the rig's backplate.

2.2 Hardware for a resilient and autonomous outdoor monitoring system

For automated long-term monitoring in outdoor conditions, all components need to be stable and resilient. This is especially true for the computer hardware setup [4], which needs to run despite hostile weather, power, and internet outages and possible manipulation attempts by visitors. In our experimental setup Figure 1, we control the sensors and collect data on mini-computers in waterproof enclosures: Raspberry Pi for the environmental sensors and the IP camera, and an Nvidia Jetson Xavier NX computer, which controls the Azure Kinect camera. While one mini-computer could control all sensing devices, we find that the Kinect demands a higher performance graphic card, than what Raspberry Pi's up to version 5 can deliver. We added the Nvidia computer to the EMA framework's working Raspberry Pi setup for the sole reason of time efficiency. Both mini-computers are set up with measures to enable autonomous and resilient handling: remote access, measures to self-heal and restart after power failures, the local buffering of all data, and submission of these to cloud storage in time with internet access.

2.3 Data storage

All measured data is pushed into cloud-based storage. Data points from sensors (luminosity, temperature, and humidity from a sensor box on the rig and weather data from a local weather station) are stored in a time series database (InfluxDB Cloud). At the same time, files from the 3D scan and IP camera are pushed onto a cloud-based file storage (One-Drive). Timestamps are used to maintain relations between the different data types. For this, a data point with related metadata is sent to the database every time a 3D scan or image is captured.

2.4 Data processing and visualization

The Azure Kinect records sensor data in the efficient Matroska Video file (.mkv) container format. These files contain tracks for storing Color, Depth, IR images, and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) that can be converted into e.g., 3D Point Clouds, images, or movies, with the Azure Kinect Software Development Kit (SDK). While continuous recording of this data is the default mode of the Kinect, we find that recording of 5 seconds has efficient resolution, which can be averaged to a single point cloud to document the changes in architectural structures over long periods, while maintaining control of file size and relation to other data. These single files are then batch-transformed into other representations, such as colored volumetric point clouds or images, which can be stacked into time-lapse movies.

2.5 Data analysis

The extensive set of captured data over time (3D files, images, environmental and weather data) allows for in-depth tracking and analysis of changes over time in overall geometry or features and the establishment of their relations. This can take place in a manual way, where point clouds from different times are compared with specific software (e.g. CloudCompare). Here the values for overall differences between point clouds are easily detected, plotted in a graph, and correlated with environmental data (Figure 6) or b) for more extensive datasets and more in-depth analysis in an automated way, which we outline in section 4 Extended Analysis: Quantified feature-based deformation analysis.

3 CASE STUDIES

We evaluate our approach in two case studies with bio-polymer panels. The first experiment investigates the simultaneous tracking of the behavior of an array of objects Azure Kinect in wide field of view mode (WFOV), while the second focuses on changes of a single object, but in high resolution with Azure Kinect in narrow field of view (NFOV) mode.

3.1 First experiment - 8 small bio-polymer panels

In the first experiment, 3D printed panels composed of collagen-based binder and reinforcing cellulose fibers [19] in different patterns and recipes are exposed to outdoor conditions on our southwest-facing rig in Copenhagen from May to August 2023. The captured data includes the 3D scans, local sensor data, images as well as data from a weather station installed on site. We attuned the interval of the 3D capture to the movement of the 3D prints and found a scan per day to be sufficient for tracking the deformation of the panels over time. The intervals between scans would ideally be 24 hours, however, the scheduled nocturnal timing is adapted by the measured weather conditions in a 6-hour window to hit the optimal condition for 3D scanning.

3.1.1 Analysis

The 8 panels show strong deformations over time (Figure 6), where the lower not mechanically fixed ends curl in all panels up to almost 90 degrees. To understand the relationship between 3D scan data and environmental conditions (Sensed data), we incorporate human intervention, which is crucial for accurately tracking changes and validating the data, ensuring the reliability and accuracy of the data interpretation. (We test the manual analysis mode on this panel), analyze the incremental geometric deviation between each 3D capture, and correlate this data to the stream of weather data in a graph. We find that the climate in the monitored periods is relatively stable with a slight tendency to higher temperatures and humidity in the second half of the period. This increase is reflected in the panel's warping, where the range, amount, and speed of changes

increase over time in the deviation analysis, from an average of 5mm in the first to 4.7mm in the second, and finally 9mm in the final period (Figure 6). The measurement of the 3D scans 2.1.5 allows us to execute an in-depth analysis. We find that the largest amount of warpage occurs on the right side of all the panels. Here we can establish a relationship to the observed wind direction by our observation on site. However, as we do not measure the microclimate wind direction, we are not able to prove this with data. The warping takes place on the free edges of the panel, as the top timber support, restrains effectively the overall warpage. Due to the massive deformation, where the lower edges curl, it is not possible to quantify the amount of change with the C2C distance analysis. The RGB values of the 3D scans also reveal color change in the panels over time as the panels changed from gray and brown color to more yellowish color due to long exposure to the sun.

Figure 6: Analysis of deformation of the small panel over time. For this diagram, we quantify the incremental geometric change of the panel at 5 points in time. From left: initial state 12.05.2023, 02.06.2023, 26.06.2023, 17.07.2023, 07.08.2023.

3.2 Second experiment - large bio-polymer panel

In the second experiment, observations from the initial 3d monitoring inform the design of a large bio-polymer panel with zones made of different recipes of the collagen bio-polymer material and support on top and bottom. The panel is installed on the monitoring rig from the beginning of December 2023 to mid-January 2024.

3.2.1 Analysis

Contrary to the first experiment, this experiment takes place in winter with low temperatures of on average 3°C and freezing temperatures in the last third of the monitored time frame (Figure 7). The panel displays the biggest overall change in the first third of the time with up to 10mm of warp. After that larger changes

occur in the two protruding areas of the panel made of a collagen recipe with added cotton fibers. These thicker 3D printed areas are more exposed to precipitation and the material seems to be more prone to expanding and reshaping. In addition to that the bottom part of the panel shows an expansion and increase in length, however, because the top and bottom are fixed, only the unrestrained edges of the panel curl forward. Despite being made of the same material, the big panel shows less change and especially warps over time. From the data, we conclude that this is due to the change in clamping conditions and weight of the big panel and largely due to the winter conditions. What can be observed in both experiments, is the impact of the different material recipes on the behavior of the panel, e.g. that panels and areas with a high degree of cotton-based material are warping more, than those without.

Figure 7: Analysis of deformation of the big panel over time. For this, we quantify the incremental geometric change of the panel at 5 points in time. From left: initial state 01.12.2023, 15.12.2023, 25.12.2023, 04.01.2024, 15.01.2024.

4 EXTENDED ANALYSIS: QUANTIFIED FEATURE-BASED DEFORMATION ANALYSIS

The analysis of deviations between point clouds, as used in the two experiments, provides a good insight into general material behavior. However, the quantification of the differences is hard to interpret, and it is challenging to identify how much each area moved, as the actual position of the million scanned points on the panel is random in each scan. This ambiguity means that any analysis is mainly a visual one and it is hard to quantify the movement of specific areas over time e.g., edge features. The manual execution of this analysis is also a time-consuming task, comprising many repetitive tasks, such as mesh cleaning, registration, computation, and composition. This forces us to limit the difference analysis to a few selected 3D captures from the huge amount of data recorded in the month-long monitoring periods. We find that ambiguities in

3D scan data, caused by radical bio-polymer geometry changes over longer periods and varied deformation rates, challenge traditional feature detection methods. Working with small increments of time between scans makes it possible to maintain a relation between the state and position of detail, as the change in e.g., a period of 24 hours is in comparison to the change over two weeks relatively small. We therefore develop a method to automate the analysis of long-term monitoring data, which can be tuned to project-specific questions and setups and takes place in the widely used Rhino/Grasshopper design environment.

4.1 Transformation and analysis in Voxel format

Our method is based on a structured understanding of the captured 3D point cloud. We achieve this through a transformation of these into Voxel models. Voxels are beneficial for our area of application, as:

- Voxels can maintain a defined total amount of subdivisions independent of scale in each captured step.
- The subdivision of a model into Voxels can be freely tuned, according to e.g. computational needs, from high resolution, where almost every captured point is represented by a single Voxel to low resolution, where voxels represent the average position of a larger array of points.
- Each Voxel can include many layers of information, such as RGB values captured by the Azure Kinect or RGB colors for height analysis. This allows for realistic visualization.
- Voxels are well-structured data and computation is faster than point clouds.

The transformation into a Voxel model allows us to track the deformation on a feature level throughout the whole capturing period (Figure 8). For this, we transform instances of the captured point clouds into models with Voxels of equal size. Voxels are created in spatial units, that include points within the pointclouds bounding box. We assume a material with a relatively linear and homogeneous behaviour, as our bio-polymer, and can assume that the relative position of a feature in the panel does not change too much between time increments of the scans. We track the relative position of a voxel in different 3D scans, by creating minimum bounding boxes for each scan and divide this into a desired number of sections. This adaptive sections are used to find intersections with the grid of voxels in each scan. In this way, it is possible to trace features, such as voxels on the edges (Figure 8) over time, and quantify the amount and vector of movement per time step and overall. The tracking results show that on average the left side of the panel warped between 27.26mm to 42.63mm while on the other side it is equal to 29.00mm to 42.05mm. Tracking voxels in the middle of the model reveals that the minimum deformation happened in this area with the amount of 16mm to 19mm.

5 EVALUATION

Reflecting on the overall process and outcomes of our long-term outdoor 3D monitoring system, we find that it fulfills the initially established criteria of autonomy and resilience, quality of data, cost efficiency, and ability to analyze data in a project-specific way.

5.1 Autonomy and resilience

Though the depth camera is specified for the indoor environment, our measures allowed for uninterrupted outdoor 3D capturing over periods of many months despite subzero temperatures and heavy rain. Interruptions occur because of human interference, such as power interruptions. Our methods to increase the resilience of the system (self-healing, buffer of data, etc.) were sufficient to uphold automatic data capture. However, repeated power outages with a frequency of several times in one hour led to the crash of the Nvidia

6 CONCLUSION

Adding the third dimension in the observation of outdoor structures provides a means to gain novel insights into an object's behavior over time. Moving from manual inspections to our approach of automated 3D capturing in small time intervals and processing provides us with means for in-depth analysis and tracking of e.g., movements of detailed areas over time. This moves the state of the art in 3D monitoring, to a new data-driven level, that allows us now to describe the way how a change happened. In our work with bio-materials it provides a mean to reason with higher confidence, why these changes occur. In a future scenario the data can be used to inform the simulation of bio-based materials. While our system is a prototype and the resolution and reach of the used camera system are limited, it points to applications in other scales and fields. A critical part of scaling and extension is the depth camera, where range, accuracy, resolution, and ability to automate are defining parameters. Alternatives to the low range and resolution Kinect like systems have to be found for larger scale architectural applications, especially since Microsoft stopped the development of their depth cameras (again) [20].

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

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